

Milestone: MS27 - Initial set of relevant data for use cases are identified

Lead Participant: BSC

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Due: January 2024

Date Of Completion: 27/03/2024

Means of Verification

- [Deliverable 7.4](#)
- [Cancer minimal dataset](#)
- [Infectious diseases dataset](#)
- [Mapping minimal datasets](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes, to finish work in D7.4

Project participants & others

BSC, Erasmus MC, UT, UH, HSR, ELIXIR Hub, UL,
Health RI

Next action steps

- Maintain collaborative efforts for harmonizing minimal datasets
- Explore establishing crosswalks for semantic unification
- GDI use-cases to identify synthetic data examples aligning with recommendations
- Collaborate with Pillar II to test GDI infrastructure and starter kit components
- Gain holistic understanding of operational processes within GDI

